

8T – Symmetry of the Coupling Constants Series under Sign Reversal – and Existence of Anti–Matter

O Manor

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Abstract:

By analyzing the primordial coupling constants series under sign reversal it is possible to get an additional perspective on the entire latitude of the new framework of the 8T, revolving around varying curvature. Analysis will be made according to first, second and third representations, i.e. net curvature, spin and the arrow of time.

Introduction

The new 8T framework regard bosons as net curvature on the matrix tensor. The net curvature are of discrete amounts and is isomorphic to the prime numbers or one. Using three theorems made on a Lorentz manifold with (3,1) signature, it was possible to calculate the magnitude of the fine structure constant. Suppose we vary the sign of the electron by equation (1.32):

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \tag{1.1}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.2}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2} = 2N_1 + 1 \tag{1.3}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2} = 2N_2 + 1 \tag{1.31}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) - (3)] + 5 \quad (1.31)$$

The coupling series does not make sense anymore; it is not in agreement with the third coupling term. Suppose we varied the discrete amount of net curvature associated with the third coupling term, i.e. the photon:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (3)] - 5 \quad (1.32)$$

Therefore, we again reached a term causing a contradiction with observation. The desired conclusion regarding the primordial series is the following: The only symmetry possible is a complete symmetry that involves reversing the sign of the entire terms of each coupling magnitude as in equation (1.33).

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [-(24 * 5) - (3)] - 5 \quad (1.33)$$

By that sign reversal of the coupling series, notice that now as opposed to the original series the direction of time is opposite:

$$-1: -30: > -128: > -850: > -9254 \dots$$

By the third representation of the arrow of time, the direction of the arrow now is reversed. That is quite similar to the CPT theorem; however, we did not use the analogue of the middle term P, only the charge reversal and time reversal in this analysis. The purpose of this assay was to analyze the symmetry under sign reversal of each coupling term. That symmetry imposes a restriction on each sub element of the coupling term, such as the photon and the electron. Such a symmetry than give rise to the existence of anti-matter. That is matter with opposite sign, which gives the exact same coupling magnitudes. As oppose to QFT which assume it is the case in order to ensure the symmetry of the "S matrix", the existence of anti-matter is due to the symmetry of the coupling magnitudes, which contains photons and electrons as part of them.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)
- [2] O. Manor. "The Coupling constants series, Spin Symmetries and Unbounded electrons" In: (2021)